

COMMUNITY RESIDENTS' PERCEPTION OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE REINTEGRATION OF REPENTANT BOKO HARAM INSURGENTS INTO THEIR COMMUNITIES IN NORTHEAST NIGERIA: EVIDENCE FROM BORNO AND YOBE STATES

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Abstract: Reintegration of ex-combatants has been a pressing issue across the globe over the past two decades. Governments and community members are concerned about accommodating ex-criminals who have surrendered their weapons and are willing to return to their communities. Borno and Yobe alone have received over 250,000 repentant Boko Haram insurgents with the aim of returning them to their communities in a meaningful and dignified manner. This study assessed the factors affecting repentant Boko Haram insurgents' reintegration into their local communities in Northeastern Nigeria. Focus group discussion was used to interview some community members regarding their perceptions of the reintegration program and their responses were analyzed using IPA technique. The study revealed that the reintegration program is illusive because the ex-criminals have a strong allegiance to their former group. Hence, it is recommended that the government take drastic measures that will cut the strong allegiance between the repentant Boko Haram members and their former group to build the trust and confidence of the local communities to accept the repentant Boko Haram members.

Keywords: Boko Haram, communities, insurgents, reintegration, residents, repentant

1.0 Introduction

Over the past two and a half decades, significant global changes have contributed to the rise in the number of incarcerated individuals. As of 2024, the incarceration rate in the United States reached 614 per 100,000 population, compared to 114 in the United Kingdom, 116 in Portugal, 109 in Canada, and 107 in France (Widra, 2024). Consequently, incarcerated individuals began to be reintegrated into their communities. The reintegration of prisoners and ex-offenders is a pressing issue facing many countries today. Perhaps, the Singapore prison services rehabilitation framework was first developed in 2000 as a deliberate operating model that guides the reformation and reintegration of their offender. This articulates a structured and comprehensive approach for all rehabilitation efforts, and ensures optimization of their limited resources by allocating programs based on

prisoners' risks and needs. Similarly, there were also instances of reintegration in Indonesia. The Circle of Peace Foundation was involved in the pioneering construction of the Al-Quran Education Park in 2017 and the renovation of the Baitul Muttaqin Mosque in Solokuro (Ashley, 2020).

African countries such as Mozambique (1991), Zimbabwe (1995), South Africa (1998), Sierra Leone (2000), Ghana (2001), Rwanda (2001), and Liberia (2006) have adopted a reconciliation and reintegration process to help bring their societies back from violence to peace. These processes were necessary to change the negative perceptions, mistrust, and ill-feelings that communities held against ex-militants and to resolve the deep community fragmentation problems.

One example of this process is the Foundation for Ethnic Harmony in Nigeria (FEHN), which, with the support of the Oil and Gas Internal Foundation (OGIF), engaged some ex-militants in a proactive reconciliation with their communities through the Community Outreach Program (COP) (Oluwaniyi, 2018). Recently, many Boko Haram fighters have surrendered themselves to the government and were reintegrated back into their communities. However, there was no idea how the local communities perceived this government's reintegration effort as many insurgents continue to surrender on a daily basis.

In addition to empowerment-focused rehabilitation efforts, Borno and Yobe have pursued several non-empowerment strategies aimed at addressing the radicalization of repentant insurgents. These efforts emphasize psychological, social, and cultural reintegration, which aims to reshape the mindset and beliefs of former insurgents. In Borno, for example, community-based reconciliation programs have been established to foster trust between repentant insurgents and the broader public. These programs often involve religious and traditional leaders, who provide moral guidance and promote religious reform to counter extremist ideologies, which are contained in the Borno model, which accepts repentant insurgents in local communities. Similarly, in Yobe, the state implemented localized de-radicalization initiatives that prioritized family and community reintegration, rather than economic empowerment. These initiatives focus on providing a safe space for former insurgents to reconnect with their cultural identities and rebuild social ties while discouraging violent ideologies through dialogue and communal support.

Previous studies conducted by Salihu and Yahaya (2021), Beth's (2021), and Bukarti (2019) focused on the NMA against Terrorism in Nigeria. Other studies largely highlight economic and vocational empowerment as the primary means of rehabilitating insurgents. These non-empowerment efforts emphasize the importance of social and psychological healing, bridging the gap between individuals and their communities, and providing a more holistic approach to countering radicalization. However, little attention has been paid to the factors affecting the reintegration of repentant Boko Haram insurgents into their local communities, and this is the gap this study intends to fill.

1.2 Study Objectives

This study has the following objectives:

- i.** Assess the effect of grievances and anger on repentant Boko Haram insurgents' reintegration into their communities.
- ii.** Assess the effect of ineffective entrepreneurship programs on retaining repentant Boko Haram insurgents to their communities.
- iii.** Assess the effect of community members' poverty and illiteracy on the repentant Boko Haram insurgents' reintegration into their communities.
- iv.** Examine the effect of fear, betrayal, and group loyalty on the repentant Boko Haram insurgents' reintegration into their local communities in Borno and Yobe States.

2.0 Clarification of Concepts

The following concepts were operationally clarified as they are often used in this study.

Reintegration: The act of bringing someone back to his or her original society, which may require him or her to become a productive and active member of their community. This may entail bringing back the repentant members of Boko Haram to their communities after they have regretted their actions and surrendered themselves to the government, indicating that they have repented and are willing to return to their original life.

Repentant: A sincere expression of regret by a member of a violent group such as the Boko Haram members who are 'willing to drop their weapons and leave the bush if they are to be accepted by society and the government, having sincerely expressed that they will not commit such offences again and are ready to join other individuals for peaceful interaction in the community.

Residents' Grievances: Grievance refers to the emotional and psychological response of individuals or communities who feel wronged, usually due to personal loss, trauma, or injustice. Residents' grievances stem from the socio-economic and emotional toll of the Boko Haram insurgency in the context of reintegration. This includes loss of life, property, displacement, and psychological distress. These grievances may shape the community's perception of the reintegration process, potentially fueling hostility toward former insurgents and creating a barrier to their successful reintegration.

Poverty: refers to the socioeconomic deprivation experienced by individuals or communities that limits their access to basic resources such as food, shelter, education, and health care. In the context of insurgency, poverty serves as a critical driver of radicalization, as impoverished individuals may view joining extremist groups as a way to escape their harsh realities. Limited financial resources can make people vulnerable to recruitment by insurgent groups that offer financial incentives or promises of socio-economic mobility.

Illiteracy: The lack of basic education, including both formal and informal education, hinders an individual's ability to critically analyze information and engage with society in an informed and constructive manner. In regions affected by insurgencies such as Boko Haram, illiteracy can fuel radicalization by making individuals more susceptible to extremist ideologies, as they may lack the education to critically evaluate religious or political narratives. Illiteracy, combined with poverty, can lead individuals to join insurgent groups as a means of survival, identity, or socio-political expression.

Vocational and Entrepreneurship Training: Vocational training refers to education and skill development programs aimed at equipping individuals with specific trade skills or technical knowledge that can be directly applied to employment. **Entrepreneurship training** involves preparing individuals to create and run their own businesses. For former insurgents, these programs are intended to offer alternative means of livelihood and reduce their dependency on extremist activities. These programs help individuals develop practical skills that can lead to sustainable employment, economic self-sufficiency, and productive reintegration into society.

2.1 Review of Related Literature

2.1.1 Effect of Grievances and Anger on the Reintegration of Repentant Boko Haram Insurgents to Their Communities

The empowerment support given to repentant members of the Boko-Haram has excavated ill feelings, anger, and grievances among community residents. Saskia (2018) noted that residents are more likely to display anger toward returnees and defectors when the militant group remains active, and the returnees themselves may be at risk of retaliatory violence. Onapanjo and Ozden (2020) also posit that there is a high possibility that unsuccessfully deradicalized members may return to the group and become more hardened to prove their loyalty to the group when faced with the challenges of anger displacement from the community. Furthermore, a failed deradicalization program diminishes the trust of citizens and combatants in non-military peace processes. Moreover, Ehiane (2019) contends that there is too much emphasis on military actions and ending support for militant ideologies. More

importantly, there is a lack of focus on the social context into which former combatants might reintegrate as well as the perceptions of the communities. While some literature exists on the role of communities in reintegration processes in Africa, most of them approach this subject from the perspective of the returnees/ex-combatants and their experiences of trying to reintegrate. Less exploration is done regarding the communities' perspectives hosting these returnees, their involvement in the reintegration programs, and their perceptions of the reintegration programs. This is surprising because the positive support and active participation of communities are logically key to the success of reintegration and rehabilitation.

According to Uguru (2010) and Ehigiator (2011), the grievances that have arisen from the successful graduation of 3112 ex-Niger Delta militants in Nigeria have not deterred the government from investing a huge amount of money for the development of the local communities and building their confidence in the region. By 2010, sixty-three percent of the newly implemented budgets in Niger-Delta will go to rebuilding the infrastructure in the affected areas. This also includes the reconstruction of the Gbaramatu kingdom, which is composed of several villages within the Delta State. The \$1.28 billion Bayelsa State project primarily focused on the reconstruction of access roads, support for youth centers, and rehabilitation and reconstruction of health facilities. Unlike the Northeastern region, where the focus was shifted toward reintegrating repentant Boko Haram members. Other scholars, such as Ebiede (2020), have challenged the government's intention toward the Reintegration program by noting that there is perceived skepticism toward the Nigerian government's genuine rationale for proffering monetary incentives to ex-combatants/militants as a means of fostering reintegration and rehabilitation. This criticism tends to breed a feeling that those who are not members of Boko Haram or even take up arms, like the militants, are less worthy of governmental attention under the program, a grievance that has seriously disrupted the re integration program.

2.1.2 Ineffective Entrepreneurship Programs on the Repentant Boko Haram Insurgents

The sustainability and effectiveness of the entrepreneurship skills training provided to repentant Boko Haram members played a key role in the success of reintegration program in Borno and Yobe States. Gbadeyan and Omobuwajo (2019) also revealed that host communities refused to accept repentant Boko Haram members, claiming that the reintegration program may not be successful until the victims of Boko Haram attacks and their communities receive support to rebuild their lives and livelihoods. Extending the kinds of skills acquisitions and vocational training available to defectors at the camp and communities and providing trainees with start-up capital and/or tools will not only empower society economically but also reduce bitterness toward ex-militants returning home with marketable skills.

People lack confidence in governmental reintegration programs, and this spans from the lack of transparency in the reintegration interventions to corrupt practices of those administering the intervention and perceived favoritism of the alleged 'repentant' combatants over the community (Ebiede, 2020). He noted that this unsustainability of packages, which was not born out of genuine intention, may bring the program to its knees. However, Uguru (2010), Oluwaniyi (2011), and Bello (2020) stated that the Niger-Delta Presidential Amnesty saw the successful reintegration of 20,192 ex-militants who surrendered about 2,760 weapons, 3,155 magazines, 287,445 ammunitions, 763 explosives, 1,090 dynamite caps, and 18 gunboats to the amnesty committee. After the end of the Amnesty, other militants who reluctantly failed to participate in the program realized the lofty benefits enjoyed by the militants who had been successfully reintegrated. This further increased the total number of repented militants to 6,166. The repented militants were provided with skills acquisition training to become self-reliant after the program. They were also reported to have a monthly allowance of \$439. These effective empowerment packages have contributed immensely to the success of the reintegration program.

Moreover, Tang (2022) established that the period of incarceration allowed the SCS an opportunity to work at reforming lives, educating them, showing them that crime does not pay, teaching them a marketable skill, giving them an education, all with one end in mind to reduce the chance of an offender reoffending after release. ICG (2021) added that to persuade low-level Boko Haram associates to defect in sizeable numbers and attract significant international support, the Nigerian authorities will need to demonstrate that the program can guide internees to graduation and reintegrate them safely and securely back into society. To date, Safe Corridor has fallen short of offering such assurances with sufficient credibility. Proper education, improved screening procedures, detention safeguards, investments in reintegration, and a public relations campaign to win political and popular support can make the program more attractive to both donors and potential defectors.

2.1.3 Effect of Poverty and Illiteracy on the Reintegration of Repentant Boko Haram Insurgents into their Local Communities

Adeyeye (2020) states that considerable success has been ascribed to Operation Safe Corridor's ability to properly educate repentant Boko Haram members to change their ideology for the better, as many of the groups took advantage of their illiteracy to recruit. For instance, in January 2018, 95 ex-Boko Haram terrorists were reportedly rehabilitated and reintegrated into society. Poverty and illiteracy have been the front wheel tire for the radicalization of Boko Haram members. This is evident in the submission of Muhammad (2018), who believes that poverty, unemployment and illiteracy also led to the emergence of the Boko Haram, because most of the members of the group engage in menial jobs for they are not well educated and this increased the tendency for poverty. Many youths joined the group as an available alternative in the face of high unemployment.

In addition, Tang (2022) noted that the period of incarceration allowed the Singapore Correctional Service an opportunity to work at reforming lives, educating and showing them that crime does not pay, teaching them a marketable skill, giving them an education, all with one end in mind to reduce the chance of an offender reoffending after release. Alao, Olusegun, and Alao (2012) agreed with the above argument, who noted that the Nigerian government should be blamed for its inability to develop policies for prompt onslaught against emerging threats, such as poverty, unemployment, and illiteracy, which contributed to the emergence of the Boko Haram insurgency. It has made it easy for the Boko-harm group to use monetary incentives to convince many youths of the poverty and illiteracy.

Moreover, Adeyeye (2020) believes that considerable success has been ascribed to the ability of the Operation Safe Corridor (OPSC) to properly educate the repentant Boko Haram members to change their ideology for the better because many of the groups took advantage of their illiteracy to recruit. Ninety-five ex-Boko Haram terrorists were reportedly rehabilitated and reintegrated into society in January 2018. In 2019, Operation Safe Corridor (OPSC) reportedly secured the release of 1,800 insurgents for rehabilitation and graduated a set of 15 convicted Boko Haram fighters. Similarly, 86 child fighters who voluntarily surrendered to the rehabilitation center in Borno State in November 2019 were also secured and handed over. Omobuwajo (2019) revealed that their previous communities refused to accept the returning ex-Boko-Haram combatant. Stating that the reintegration program may not be successful until the victims of Boko Haram attacks and their communities receive support to reconstruct their lives and livelihoods. Extending the kinds of skills acquisitions and vocational training available to defectors at the camp and communities and providing trainees with start-up capital and/or tools will not only empower society economically but also reduce bitterness toward ex-militants returning home with marketable skills. According to him, this educational investment and poverty alleviation program may help prevent the occurrence of such a situation.

2.1.4 Effect of Fear, Betrayal, and Group Loyalty on the Reintegration of Repentant Boko Haram Insurgents into their Local Communities

Due to the tragic experience of the Boko Haram insurgents' activities, community residents feared that repentant Boko Haram members might be coming back as spies to target some individuals (Ebiede, 2020). Furthermore, there was a perceived resistance to former Boko Haram combatants because communities feared they might act as spies and informants in triggering more violence. When the residents were not even sure whether it was a true repentance and the government had already given them such priorities, then anger displacement was imminent, which might include resistance and rejection on the part of community residents.

However, Club and Tapley (2018) contend that the Nigerian deradicalisation program has a broader function as long as it provides former combatants with 'scripts' of disengagement and functions as a brand, signaling to communities that former combatants have repented and are 'better citizens, imbued with genuine nationalism' that resonate with local communities. Club (2018) also established that one of the difficulties that undermines the de-radicalization program's efforts is the push-back against the re-integration of former Boko Haram communities. This is because reintegrated former combatants will continue to spread Boko Haram's support for violence even if the group is defeated, and there is skepticism on those former combatants who denounced violence. However, the surveillance of reintegrated former combatants may reduce the likelihood of them re-engaging in violence. On the contrary, Saskia (2018) noted that there is a big challenge to the reintegration program in Nigeria, where residents are more likely to distrust returnees and defectors when the militant group remains active. He further stated that the returnees themselves may be at risk of retaliatory violence, especially when the residents of local communities were afraid of betrayal from the returnees. Bukarti (2019) revealed that the majority of returning repentant continue to face serious stigmatization from the community. The issue of trust became the bone of contention, adding to the fear of being associated with a criminal, particularly with the fact that many repentants returned to their initial group to prove their loyalty to the group.

2.2 Empirical Review

Bello (2020) conducted a study titled "An assessment of regional counter terrorism strategies in the Lake Chad Basin: a case study of Boko Haram insurgency" that examined the level of cooperation among the affected countries and appraised the efforts of the Nigerian Government and the Nigerian Army in combating the Boko Haram Insurgency in the Lake Chad Basin. The study used a mixed method, and the findings revealed that no single factor can explain the emergence of insurgent groups, particularly Islamist militancy (Boko Haram), in the region. Understanding the context and environment through which this has taken place is significant to ultimately understand the movement itself. The research, therefore, concludes that military and security agencies have made some development in limiting the activities of Boko Haram insurgents, and their own practices have, at times, been ungainly and have included violations of human rights, adding to the sense of insecurity and alienation that increase divisions among displaced persons and communities.

Another study conducted by Salihu and Yahaya, (2021) "the relevance of community involvement in military counterinsurgency operations in north eastern Nigeria" the aim of the research was to examine Nigeria's framework for countering Boko Haram beyond the conventional kill or capture approach to more people-oriented interventions. The study utilized qualitative textual analysis of secondary data. The study revealed that the use of military force is counterproductive given its state-referent orientation. Therefore, the study concludes that the use of force has heightened the effect of the conflict on millions of civilians who have fled their communities in fear of Boko Haram and military highhandedness.

A study conducted by Colouries (2019), entitled "The Roles of Communities in the Effective Reintegration of Ex-Offenders in the Lake Chad Basins," examined the role of communities in the reintegration of violent ex-offenders in Cameroon, Nigeria, Niger, and Chad. The study employs a mixed methodology. The study revealed that more positive responses on reintegration came from communities that experienced a lower rate of violence.

Communities also described potential methods that VEOs can use to achieve reconciliation and community acceptance, which included asking the community for forgiveness, asking forgiveness from God, and swearing an oath for not going violence again. The study concludes that communities have strongly resisted reintegration for various reasons.

It can be seen from the empirical studies reviewed that while Colouries (2019) focused on the roles of communities in the effective reintegration of violent extremist offenders in the lake chad basin countries, focused on demobilization, rehabilitation and reintegration of repentant Boko Haram insurgents in Nigeria, this research specifically focuses on the role of the government in the reintegration of repentant Boko Haram members in Borno and Yobe States. Again, Bello (2020) and Calories (2019) relied heavily on the mixed method. However, this study undertakes a qualitative analysis of the role of the government in the reintegration of repentant Boko Haram members in Borno and Yobe States. Therefore, little attention has been given to studying the factors affecting the reintegration of repentant Boko Haram members in Borno and Yobe States. This study addresses the existing contextual gap left out by those researchers.

3.0 Methodology

This study employs a qualitative approach using FGDs to explore the factors affecting the smooth reintegration of ex-Boko Haram combatants into their communities in Borno and Yobe States, Nigeria. A total of 18 participants selected through purposive sampling were divided into two groups of 9 individuals representing key stakeholders: residents of local communities, members of local vigilante groups, security personnel, ex-combatants of Boko Haram, and community leaders. Data collection involved semi-structured interviews within the FGD format to allow for in-depth discussions of personal experiences and perceptions. IPA was employed to analyze the data, focusing on how participants make sense of the reintegration process and the meanings they attach to their experiences.

4.0 Presentation of the Results

The findings of this study were presented in line with the study's specific objectives.

4.1 Grievances and Anger

Grievances and anger were the cornerstones of the successful reintegration of repentant Boko Haram members. Grievance is a state of lack of happiness, while anger is a direct transfer of sour emotion. Grievance is usually a transfer of anger to a particular individual thinking that is part of the cause of your anger. The oral interview conducted with respondents I1 and I3 is summarized below:

I do not support reintegrating repentant insurgents back into our community for any purpose. It actually hurts to forgive Boko Haram members. Why is it that the government only provides skills acquisition training and startup capital to repentant Boko-Haram members? What about the victims of the Boko-Haram insurgency? What about those of us who lost their loved ones to the threat of the Boko-Haram attack and are in dire need of empowerment packages? (I1) and (I3).

The findings in Section 4.1 correspond with the work of Saskia (2018) on the challenges of reintegration in Nigeria. It notes that residents are more likely to display anger toward returnees and defectors when the militant group remains active, and returnees themselves may be at risk of retaliatory violence. These have indicated a show of grievance about the whole process of reintegration, including the skills acquisition training and empowerment packages given to repentant Boko Haram members.

On the issue of grievances and anger, in an interview with I5 and I7, it was revealed that

...My perception is that a terrorist is a terrorist. The government does not need to waste resources for rehabilitation, and they should be convicted in a court of law and receive a penalty equivalent to their offense. They bragged about the number of people they killed... ” (I5) and (I7).

This interview with (I5) and (I7) concurs with the view point of Margaret and Besing-mengla (2020), who posit that many people in society continue to label ex-offenders as criminals who do not favor the rehabilitation of prisoners and the reintegration of ex-convicts into society. This is despite the fact that when a person serves imprisonment, he has paid for the crime he committed. This is not true as society continues to condemn ex-prisoners, making only a few of them reintegrate into society.

Similarly, (I5) and (I7) demonstrate the degree of grievance that the reintegration program holds against returning Boko Haram members:

“...this has not been fair; in the first place, he was a criminal and later a celebrated hero who is enjoying the benefit of free education, including business startup packages. This will motivate others to determine crime as a lucrative opportunity. That is treason; you are to give them education. This is the opinion of many here. We see it as an act of government support for terrorism. There are citizens who are deserving of free education. I think the government should consider them first...” (I5 and I7).

These opinions corroborate the works of Onapanjo and Ozden (2020), who argued that the design and implementation of repentant Boko Haram members' reintegration have structural weaknesses that may further contribute to the problem of violent extremism. That is if the program is not redesigned to incorporate community residents who were at the receiving end of Boko Haram perpetrated violence, then they can become a strong saboteur to the success of the program because of their anger level. As for the position of I5 and I7 interpreted from their response, they are ready to displace their anger on any of the repentant Boko Haram returnees. The position of I5 and I7 was also supported by Akinyetun (2020), who stressed that there was a perceived resistance to former Boko Haram combatants because communities feared they might act as spies and informants in triggering more violence. When the residents were not even sure whether it was a true repentance and the government had already given them such priorities, then anger displacement was imminent, which might include resistance and rejection on the part of community residents.

4.2 Poverty and Illiteracy

Poverty is any form of social, physical, and psychological deprivation suffered by a person in society that makes him vulnerable and mal-adjusted. The responses from I14 and I18 revealed that poverty was the major cause of the Boko Haram crises. In summary:

“...Poverty is the source of crime, so the startup capital given to them is good. In addition to illiteracy being the reason behind their involvement in such acts, poverty is also a bigger factor. In the very first time, the Boko Haram group used to pay its members a huge sum of money. To cut this financial dependency, they must be supported financially...” (I14) and (I18).

The views of (I14) and (I18) converged and concurred with the opinion of Chinonso (2018), who believes that poverty, unemployment, and illiteracy also led to the emergence of the Boko Haram, because most of the group's members engage in menial jobs because they are not well educated, and this increased the tendency for poverty. Many youths joined the group as an available alternative despite high unemployment. The majority of the youths joined Boko Haram because of poverty and illiteracy, usually fueled by misinterpretation of religious doctrine. The study assumed that Boko Haram insurgency is more associated with socio-economic conditions than with a weak criminal justice system. However, the response showed that the deepening system is vital in the spread of Boko Haram ideology.

On illiteracy, I1, I2, I3, and I4 added the following:

“...education can go a long way in changing their ideology. For me, indoctrination through misinterpretation of religious doctrines can be eliminated through proper education.” (I1, I2, I3, and I4).

These responses corroborated with the work of the International Crisis Group (ICG) (2021) that to persuade low-level Boko Haram associates to defect in sizeable numbers and attract significant international support, the Nigerian authorities will need to demonstrate that the Reintegration program can guide internees to graduation and safely and securely reintegrate them back into society.

It is good to give them education, because in most cases, the pioneers of this group capitalize on illiteracy to recruit people. The government should educate them. In this way, they can change their ideology when they are informed. They needed to be educated in both Western and Qur'anic education. This can actually change the way they think (I11 and I16).

These responses aligned with the study of Akinyetun (2020), who ascribed considerable success to the ability of Operation Safe Corridor to properly educate repentant Boko-Haram members to change their ideology for the better because many of the groups took advantage of their illiteracy to recruit. Similarly, Adeyeye (2020) reported that in January 2018, 95 ex-Boko Haram terrorists were rehabilitated and reintegrated into society.

4.3 Ineffective Entrepreneurship Program

Entrepreneurship skills is a process by which entrepreneurs, individuals, institutions, corporations, and governments create economic and commercial activities necessary for the improvement of the standard of living of the society. Regarding the ineffectiveness of the entrepreneurship skills training delivered to repentant Boko-Hara members, I2, I3, and I17 viewed:

"In Nigeria, I don't think it is realistic." Most of them cannot rely on that skill for survival... this is not sustainable...the truth is it's not sustainable, because the majority of the rehabilitation centers are being taken care of by non-governmental organizations. By the time they left, these initiatives might collapse; the government does not even take care of its own investment and instead speaks more of another initiative. In the end, it will all be politics" (I2, I3, and I17).

This can be concurred with the work of Ebiede (2020), who claimed that people lack confidence in governmental reintegration programs. Instances of this span from the lack of transparency in the reintegration interventions to corrupt practices of those administering the intervention and perceived favoritism of the alleged 'repentant' combatants over the community. Therefore, this finding appears to be unique and claims that vocational skills training delivered to repentant Boko Haram members is not sustainable and cannot sustain them after rehabilitation.

I7, I8, and I9 added that

...it is not sustainable; not only repentant Boko Haram members but all the entrepreneurship training that the government gives to people everywhere in Nigeria is a scam. It is unrealistic and not practicable, nothing but a business for the contractors and other responsible authority... I do not believe in giving them so-called entrepreneurship training. It will later be politicized; some people might be benefiting at the expense of the repentant members of Boko Haram. Therefore, the policy is symbolic. Therefore, I do not think it is sustainable (I7, I8, and I9).

The interviews with I7, I8, and I9 are in the same vein as the findings of Ike, Jiddong, and Ayobi (2024), whose studies revealed that agonizing experiences and resentment toward incentives provided to former defectors limit successful reintegration, whereas using trauma-informed intervention to address community needs could improve reintegration. It concludes that the involvement of affected victims and the community in the design of reintegration programs is crucial to its success. Although not the same, the point of dichotomy between the two findings is that I7, I8, and I9 believe that vocational skills training is not sustainable.

4.4 Fear, Betrayal, and Group Loyalty

In several occasions, the Boko Haram members claimed to have repented but later despise community trust and return to their initial gang (Ike, et al. 2021). This had diminished the trust of the community, making them fear whether all the repentant Boko Haram members coming in bulk would later betray them for their own group. In an interview, I6 revealed the following

It's good to empower them, but I don't support giving them money. Money can be used to do many things, especially when the society has not yet repented. The government can empower entrepreneurs with equipment to start a business but not with money (I6).

Although residents criticize the idea of giving money, the criticism tends to breed a feeling that those who are not members of Boko Haram or even take up arms, like the militants, are less worthy of government attention under the program. As such, reintegration programs were perceived as legalizing criminal acts, rewarding violence, giving criminals power, fame and money and glorifying recklessness while the innocent law-abiding citizens suffered as victims and remained unemployed with little financial opportunities.

Further, I5 and I7 added the following

When you give them money, you also empower them to be stronger than you are. They have repented and have enjoyed all these packages and still return to the group. They use the money to buy weapons and food for their allies in the bush (I5 and I7).

This finding slightly contradicts the findings of Club and Tapley (2018), who stated that the Nigerian deradicalisation program has a broader function in that it provides former combatants with 'scripts' of disengagement and functions as a brand, signaling to communities that former combatants have repented and are 'better citizens, imbued with genuine nationalism' that resonate with local communities. As far as the responses to I5 and I7 are concerned, the local community cannot resonate well with the repentant Boko Haram members for fear of betrayal and other anomalies.

I13 and I15 also believed that

"... I don't think they can change their ideology. From a practical perspective, the majority of the repentant members who passed through rehabilitation centers now returned to reunite with their group to prove their loyalty to the group. Some of them still communicate with their allies even after leaving the group and talk about their life in the group. Of all the repentant Boko Haram members that have gone through rehabilitation, almost all of them have now returned to their initial group if not for those kept at Maiduguri." (I13 and I15)

The views of I13 and I15 were corroborated with the work of Ebiede (2020), who posits that there was a perceived resistance to former Boko Haram combatants because communities feared they might act as spies and informants in triggering more violence. Many residents thought that repentant Boko Haram members could still go back to their group, fearing that they could betray them after trusting them.

Regarding group loyalty, I5 and I7 shared their opinions on

"When you give them money, you also empower them to be stronger than you are." They have repented in the first place and have enjoyed all these packages and still return to the group. They use the money to buy weapons and food for their allies in the bush.... (I5 & I7).

This stand corroborated the findings of Boye, Wakili, and Audu (2024), whose findings revealed that the application of a non-kinetic approach through the OPSC has facilitated the Boko Haram crisis in the Northeast sub-region to some extent. This is because some Boko Haram insurgents have repented and accepted the FGN's peace initiative. On the other hand, some community members affected by the Boko Haram insurgency expressed fears and were unhappy about the amnesty and the reintegration process due to the group's atrocity. Furthermore, a failed deradicalization program diminishes the trust of citizens and combatants in non-military peace processes. Therefore, repentant Boko Haram members are highly likely to return to their initial group.

Again, I5 and I7 further added the following

“I don’t think they can change their ideology.” If you look at it from a practical perspective, the majority of the repentant who passed through rehabilitation centers now went back to reunite with their group to prove their loyalty to the group. Their ideology can never change. Some of them still communicate with their allies even after leaving the group. So, a change of ideology is never an option for them...” (I5 and I7).

This finding also corroborated the findings of A. Sambo and A. Ahmed (2024). Former members of violent extremist groups often experience violence, mistrust, and shame upon reintegrating into their communities. This is particularly true when conflict victims have not received proper assistance. Communities’ express concerns about the safety and security risks associated with reintegrating former Boko Haram fighters, with some fearing it will intensify existing animosities and combatants in non-military peace processes. The finding further justifies the claim of Mercy Corps (2019). The reintegration of ex-combatants into civilian society is challenging because they lack the necessary skills and education to obtain work. Local economies in areas afflicted by violent conflicts are often severely harmed, resulting in high rates of poverty, food insecurity, unemployment, suffering, poor governance, and religious fanaticism.

4.5 Findings

This study found that community residents were not happy about the empowerment packages given to the repentants and had the perception that it can only strengthen them and cannot change their ideology. This can be seen from the responses of I2 and I3 in 4.1 (Grievances and Anger), where they stated that “I do not support reintegrating the repentant insurgents back to our community for whatever purpose.” It actually hurts to forgive Boko-Haram members”. Similarly, in the responses to I5 and I7, it was deduced that this will motivate others to determine crime as a lucrative opportunity.

The study also found that the majority of the youths joined Boko Haram because of poverty and illiteracy, usually fueled by misinterpretation of religious doctrine. Therefore, the study assumed that the Boko Haram insurgency is more associated with socioeconomic conditions than with a weak criminal justice system. This can be seen from the responses of I14 and I18 in 4.2 (**Poverty and Illiteracy**) where they claimed that “...Poverty is the source of crime, so the startup capital given to them is good.” Besides, illiteracy being the reason behind their involvement in such acts, poverty is also a bigger factor. It can also be seen in the responses of I2, I3, and I4, where they claimed that “...education can go a long way in changing their ideology.” Meanwhile, it is the view of the researcher that indoctrination through misinterpretation of religious doctrines can be eliminated through proper education.”

The findings also revealed that the entrepreneurship program provided to repentant Boko Haram members is ineffective, adding that the program is politically motivated and few people will benefit from the program at the expense of the repentant Boko Haram members. This can be seen in 4.3 (**Ineffective Entrepreneurship Program**) from the interview outcomes with I2, I3, and I17, where they unanimously agreed that “In Nigeria, I don’t think it is realistic.” Most of them cannot rely on that skill for survival... this is not sustainable...the truth is it is not sustainable. Not only repentant Boko Haram members but all the entrepreneurship training that the government gives to people everywhere in Nigeria is a scam.

Finally, the study findings revealed that the majority of the respondents are in despair and fear of betrayal. They doubt the reality that these repentant Boko Haramists have actually repented for real; they still see them as potential criminals, and perhaps this could be associated with their previous experiences about the repentant members. This can be seen from the responses of I13 and I15 (**fear, betrayal, and group loyalty**), where they stated that they do not think they can change their ideology. From a practical perspective, the majority of the

repentant members who passed through rehabilitation centers now went back to reunite with their group to prove their loyalty to the group.

5.0 Conclusion

This study used a qualitative approach using FGDs to study the factors affecting the smooth reintegration of ex-Boko Haram combatants into their communities in Borno and Yobe States, Nigeria. A total of 18 participants selected through purposive sampling were divided into two groups of 9 individuals representing key stakeholders. Data were collected through focus group discussion and analyzed using the interpretative phenomenological analysis technique.

The study concludes that the reintegration of repentant Boko Haram members in Yobe and Borno State was affected by grievances and anger displacement from community members, noting that they were unhappy about the empowerment packages given to the repentant Boko Haramists. The study also concludes that the majority of youths joined Boko Haram because of poverty and illiteracy, which is usually fueled by false religious interpretations. Therefore, the study assumed that Boko Haram insurgency is more associated with socioeconomic conditions than with a weak criminal justice system. Again, it was concluded that the entrepreneurship program provided to repentant Boko Haram members is ineffective, adding that the program is politically motivated and few people will benefit from the program at the expense of the repentant members. This study also concludes that effective reintegration of the repentant Boko Haramist is affected by fear, betrayal, and group loyalty of the repentant Boko Haramist, with the majority of the respondents being in despair and doubting their true intentions.

5.1 Recommendations

All hands must be on deck to ensure adequate community mobilization, sensitization, and awareness to reduce the level of stigmatization experienced by repentant Boko Haram returnees in their local communities.

As a matter of urgency, policy makers should consider poverty alleviation and educational development of the citizens, because they are the major sources of conflict.

There is a need to formulate a policy to ensure genuine commitment and sustainability of the empowerment packages given to repentant Boko Haram members and to ensure community integration. This will bring balance of interest, which is a measure for reconciliation and peace building.

The government should liaise with traditional institutions, media, and advocacy groups to create awareness and enlighten the receiving host communities to build trust.

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